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OVERSIGHT FUNCTIONS OF THE NATIONAL ASSEMBLY IN NIGERIA: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

This paper examines legislative oversight and executive accountability in the public account committees of the National Assembly in the wake of the growing decay in the accountability of public office holders in Ministries Departments and Agencies. This has call to question the supposed constitutional role that the legislatures and the national assembly are playing by way of legislative oversight on the executive arm. The purpose of this study is to serve as a baseline for examining the legislative oversight role of the national assembly, by this the study intends to identify areas of oversight in need of improvement to enhance the executive accountability. The study adopted the mixed survey method of data analysis, Using simple percentages and tables. The study relied heavily on secondary sources such as books, journals, articles, periodical, government reports and publications, magazines, unpublished manuscript, and conference papers; also, on primary sources such as interviews and questionnaires. The study revealed that that there has not been sufficient legislative oversight role played in the manner that can result in enhance executive Accountability. It also found that legislative oversight role of the national assembly was active during the 8th assembly but became largely docile and passive in the 9th assembly, which made the legislature play a relatively weak role in promoting executive accountability. The study concluded that that corruption and leadership collusion by both the legislatures and executive during appropriation, approvals and management of infrastructural development funds to be the major challenge weakening legislative oversight and in extension the accountability of the executive. It was recommended that the National Assembly establish its own independent network or machinery through which requisite information and data about the activities of various governmental ministries, Departments and Agencies could be generated; and for scholars and academics to do more as regarding the absence of a constitutional provision empowering the legislature to determine punishments for offenders which often creates a lacuna exploited by the executive and this hampers the ability of the legislature to see oversight to a logical end.

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INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, the legislature uses oversight as a mechanism to drive accountability, It's worth is measured not only by the quality of intellectual debate in the parliament but also by the level of oversight role it played on the executive arm to not only ensure implementation of projects and policies but also achieve better accountability (Jooji, 2019). Increasingly, legislative oversight role is gaining attention because it shines the spotlight on many critical issues which enable lawmakers and the general public to make informed judgments about executive performance. In recent times, legislative oversight is increasingly becoming important because of the impact it has on the role government plays to achieve public order, stable economy, and provision of public goods, executive moderation of the excesses of multinational and giant corporations, globalization and international politics and so many other factors that affects the functioning of government. The present level of poverty and infrastructural deficit and/or decay in the developing world have made it even more important, but this challenge is yet to be identified in these economies creating an unusual reaction in the form of extra-constitutional means in seeking changes.

Legislative oversight of the executive arm is designed to ensure executive compliance with statutory requirements and legislative intent, improve the efficiency, effectiveness and economy of governmental operations, evaluate programme performance, prevent executive encroachment on legislative prerogatives and powers. It is also designed to investigate alleged instances of poor administration, arbitrary and capricious behaviour, abuse, waste, dishonesty, and fraud as well as to assess the executives ability to manage and implement programme objectives, review and determine federal financial priorities and ensure that the executive policies reflects the public interest. These highlighted roles are universal but to what extent have these roles added to improve better accountability that drives implementation of infrastructural development projects wherever there are sited.

Since the beginning of the Fourth Republic, there have been instances where the oversight function of the legislature have challenged the executive; for instance, in 2001 the committee on Public accounts investigated the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and the defunct National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) and raised a lot of controversies on the activities of their administrative bodies. These interventions by the senate unraveled many sharp practices and secret bank accounts maintained by public officials and, the chairman of the Senate Committee on Media and communications in the 6th National Assembly, Sen. Ayogu Eze disclosed that several ministries, parastatals and agencies were keeping between 200 and 300 billion in such illegal accounts in the past four years (Punch Newspapers, January 4, 2008, p. 17).

In situations as above, each House of the National Assembly has the power under Section 67 of the Constitution to summon and question the minister in charge or whose Ministry has responsibility for the government agency concerned, this was the case when the then minister of Aviation, Dr (Mrs) Kema Chikwe and the then Director General of the Bureau for public enterprises (BPE) were summoned to appear before the senate committee on privatization of the Nigerian Airways Limited (NAL) and the establishment of new national airlines. The secret deals of the ministry were exposed and the plans to purchase the assets of NAL under shrouded circumstances were scuttled. The most infamous exercise of the investigative powers of the national assembly was the investigation into the Petroleum Trust Development Fund (PTDF) saga. The Senate Review Committee Reports on the PTDF concluded that both President Olusegun Obasanjo and vice President Atiku

Abubakar were guilty of breaching the laws setting up the fund and misapplying its ample funds without achieving a meaningful infrastructural development (Adamolekun, 2010).

From the foregoing, it is clear that the connection between legislative oversight role has always been understood in the light of law-making and hardly understood in the logic that the oversight role allowing the legislature to question, check, verify, scrutinize, inspect, examine, criticize, censure, challenge and call government to account can actually improve accountability and the performance of the national executives.

Conceptual Framework

According to Ndoma-Egba (2012), legislative oversight refers to the power of the legislature to review, monitor and supervise government agencies, programmes, activities and policy implementation strategies of the executive arm of government. It is meant to be the eyes and the voice, and to embody the will and wisdom of its constituents. On his part, Anyaegbunam (2010) observes that 'legislative oversight entails the continuing review by the legislature of the effectiveness of the executive in carrying out its mandate'. The legislature, in essence, plays the role of an umpire ensuring that the players (government and the bureaucracy) abide strictly by the 'rules' of the game (as provided by the legislature) and where it fails to comply by such rules, the legislature, as umpire, raises a red flag through the machinery of its oversight functions. In other words, the discussion about oversight is very vital and can be said to be at the kernel of all legislative engagements. Furthermore, the legislature monitors and asks questions of the activities of the executive and its agencies (such as ministries, departments, parastatals etc.) in order to ensure good governance and accountability (Nwangwu, 2014).

The notion of legislative oversight evokes the study of executive accountability. To Asimiyu et al. (2018), accountability exists when there is a relationship where an individual or institution, and the performance of tasks or functions by that individual or institution, are subject to another's oversight, direction, or request that they provide information or justification for their actions. Buttressing the notion of accountability, Ganghof & Eppner (2019) opined that the concept of accountability implies that the actors being held accountable have obligations to act in ways that are consistent with accepted standards of behavior and that they will be sanctioned for failures to do so.

Empirical Review

According to Agbedi et al. (2020), an article titled 'Oversights Functions of the National Assembly in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges' these authors relied on content analysis of transcribed interviews and participant observations to argue that the oversight functions of national legislatures of modern representative democracies have been accorded premium in the smooth functioning of democracy. The existing literature in the case of Nigeria, however, remains inadequate and segmented, despite the many media vibes about the activities of lawmakers in the country's fledgling democracy. Thus, these writers look at the case of the National Assembly in Nigeria, focusing on the challenges militating against the conduct of its oversight functions between 2007 and 2017. The authors further argued that the effective performance of oversight functions of the National Assembly is affected by several limiting factors, which includes lack of adequate statutory funding. In the same vein, the dearth of expertise on the part of legislators and clerks are major barriers to effective performance. Therefore, among the recommendations regarding the issue of unhealthy interference of the executive in the affairs of the legislature, funds required for oversight activities should be provided early enough to enhance effective

performance. This present study agrees with the findings of these authors that the legislature should avoid government agencies providing the money and other resources they need to be able to carry out their oversight duties.

According a study conducted by [Ebonugwu \(2022\)](#), an article on 'Legislative Oversight and Accountability: A Study of the 8th Senate Committees on Power, Works and Housing'. This author utilized data from interviews, in addition to copious evidence derived from previous studies in the field. The author argues that the National Assembly of the Federal Republic of Nigeria is widely perceived by the public to be inept in the area of legislative oversight. It understands the basis for this reputation, by identifying the problems associated with oversight performance through revisiting the origins of legislative practice in Nigeria particularly, the activities of the Senate Committees on Power, Works and Housing' (2015-2019) are thoroughly probed. The writer argues that it is apparent that effective legislative oversight is a precursory measure to the attainment of good governance goals. A series of events placed the Eight National Assembly in the sport-light of a rising conversation on oversight performance. Constitutional issues, budget delays and poor performance, inconclusiveness of high-profile investigation into corrupt practices and breach of public trust and the unsavory role of some legislators in managing the crises are some of the serious issues examined. Findings were laid out in an analytical manner, coming to the conclusion that the performance of oversight functions can only translate to socio-economic benefits for Nigerians if and when sections of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria are amended, when legislators are the inventive in advancing the national interest over self-interest and political party affiliations, Also, maximum cooperation from the executive arm of government will make it a realizable dream.

In the study by [Fatile & Adejuwon \(2023\)](#), an article on 'Legislative Oversight as Accountability Mechanism: The Nigerian Perspective' the authors argue that in Nigeria, like other countries all over the world, the legislature performs oversight functions to stop the excesses of the executive arm of government and to check wastages in governance which is considered one of the ends of democracy. Considering the great responsibility assigned by the constitution, one would expect that the legislative power would be balanced with a high degree of public accountability which is the hallmark of modern democratic governance. In this paper, the oversight functions of the legislature to scrutinize, and oversee executive action and any organ of state are brought to the front burner. It examines the constitutional provisions expressing powers of the National Assembly on oversight; current and new mechanisms for oversight and accountability; coordination amongst the spheres of government. The chapter reveals that the legislature has not lived up to the expectation of Nigerians in terms of entrenching accountable and transparent governance that will guarantee good governance for the benefit of citizens. The chapter further reveals that legislative oversight which is a crucial function of the legislature has been severally compromised and often used as a hunting dog. The paper concludes that for effective functioning, the legislature should be insulated from the influence of the executive which is sometimes counter-productive in entrenching accountable governance since such influence tends to sway the minds of the legislators from the serious business of law-making. This present study aligns with arguments of this author.

Structural Functionalism Theory

The study considered the structural functionalism theory of [Merton \(1948\)](#), [Spencer \(1903\)](#), [Almond and Powell \(1970\)](#), all cited in [DeRosso \(2003\)](#) to guide understanding of the

role that legislative oversight plays in improving the implementation of infrastructural development in a society. Structural Functionalism theory sees society as a complex system whose parts (one of which is the national assembly/the legislature) work together (with the executive and judicial organs of government) to promote solidarity and stability particularly through provision of adequate infrastructural facilities that supports livelihood in a given society. In this sense the legislature is a part of the entire system that must not only work well but also playing its role together, with other parts of the complex system for solidarity and stability to be experienced otherwise, it may lead to issues such as infrastructural decay or dearth of infrastructure that raises livelihood issues due to lack of solidarity and instability.

Functionalism was also vital in understanding the nexus between the roles played by both the legislature and the executive in a society like Nigeria by way of the legislative oversight function. Nigeria operates as an institution with different bodies or units functioning towards an agreement, when these contributions by the various units are positive, there will be less pressure state and private citizens but when the inputs from the sectors (for instance through legislative oversight) become negative, the consequences are also reflected in the dearth/decay of public infrastructure. The structural functionalist approach is relevant to understanding how the various institutions in the environment works, who does what and how the divers functionalities of units contribute either positively or negatively to the final functioning of the system. This approach looks at society through a macro-level orientation, which is a board focus on the social structures that shape society as a whole, and believes that society has evolved like organisms (DeRosso, 2003). Also, this approach looks at both social structures and functions, it addresses society as whole in terms of the functions of its constituent elements; namely norms, customs, traditions, and institutions (national assembly and oversight role).

METHODOLOGY

This study is a mixed survey and data was generated from their natural setting. purposive sampling to select those that were considered within the confines of the study population, thus the target population is as follows: 469 elected law makers drawn from the committees (in the Senate and the house of representative) in the 8th, 9th and 10th National Assembly; 2570 support staffs (from senate and the house of Representative) of the National Assembly, Representatives of the Federal ministry of Finance Abuja (286), and Representatives from Centre for Democracy and Governpance(44) totaling **3,369**. The study adopted determination formula in social sciences propounded by Taro Yammane (1967) as sample size determination formula for the study which is 400. Questionnaire was administered by the researcher and key informant interviews (KII) interview method were also used as the primary instruments of data collection.

The qualitative data collected were analysed with the aid of content analysis to form opinion pieces in the work. As for the interviews conducted the result were transcribed into themes and narratives. The quantitative data collected was presented, analyzed, and interpreted through the use of frequency tables and simple percentage. This became necessary in order to give vivid description of all relevant variables in the survey conducted.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS**Table 1: Challenges of Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability in the National Assembly**

S/N	Challenges of Legislative Oversight and Infrastructural Development in AMAC	Strongly Agreed		Agreed		Disagreed		Strongly Disagreed		Undecided	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	MDAs supplying of inaccurate information ostensibly to either impress the National Assembly of good performance or to attract the sympathy of the legislative body for increased budgetary allocation is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability.	89	24	163	44	55	14.8	63	17	0	0
2	The issue of Corruption, nepotism and Ethnic loyalty is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability.	104	28	214	57.8	28	7.5	24	6	0	0
3	Personal interests and ambition of the legislators is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability.	110	29.7	143	38.6	100	27	17	4.5	0	0
4	Lack of co-operation and conflicts in the performance of oversight functions between the executive and legislature is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability.	127	34	149	40	84	22.7	10	2.7	0	0
5	Lack of solid legislative framework for oversight is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability.	113	30.5	206	55.6	39	10.5	12	3.2	0	0
6	Inefficient monitoring and evaluation of infrastructural projects is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in	123	33	178	48	60	16	9	2	0	0

	Driving Executive Accountability.										
7	Docile citizenry is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability.	116	31	134	36	78	21	42	11	0	0

Source: Field Survey April, 2024

NB: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

The table above reveals that 89 (24%) strongly agreed and 163 (44%) agreed to the assertion that MDAs supplying of inaccurate information ostensibly to either impress the National Assembly of good performance or to attract the sympathy of the legislative body for increased budgetary allocation is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability. This represents the response of the majority of the sampled respondents of about 68% and therefore, it can be established that there is need to address the policy challenge particularly in this area. The minority view stood at only 32%. In the same vein, majority of the respondents about 85.8% argued that the issue of Corruption, nepotism and Ethnic loyalty is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability as against only 14.2% who were opposed to this view.

Again, about 68.3% of respondents argue that Personal interests and ambition of the legislators is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability, whereas only 31.7% respondents held the minority view on this question. Similarly, about 74% of respondents argue that lack of co-operation and conflicts in the performance of oversight functions between the executive and legislature is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability, whereas only 26% respondents held the minority view on this question.

More so, about 86.1% of respondents argue that Lack of solid legislative framework for oversight is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability, whereas only 13.9% respondents held the minority view on this question. The table further revealed that 123 (33%) of the respondents and 178 (48%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively, a total of 81% respondents were positive to the assertion that Inefficient monitoring and evaluation of infrastructural projects is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability. Nevertheless, about 19 held to an opposing view.

The table further revealed that 116 (31%) of the respondents and 134 (36%) of them strongly agreed and agreed respectively, a total of 67% were positive to the assertion that Docile citizenry is a challenge that hinders Legislative Oversight in Driving Executive Accountability. Nevertheless, about 33 respondents were opposed to the view.

The implication of these issues shows that the path to the legislative oversight role that would have adequately monitored, evaluated and investigated the executive toward better accountability in finances and public affairs was strewed with multiple challenges that hampered and still hinders oversight and in extension hinders executive improved accountability.

Felix Okwonkwo in this interview (2024) argues that the issue of lack of established democratic culture has been a disturbing challenge to oversight duty, the fact that Nigeria's democracy is young is a significant factor militating against legislative oversight in Nigeria. According to him, the debilitating effect of prolonged military rule in Nigeria has produced

negative consequences that continue to haunt individuals and institutions in Nigeria. The legislature is not an exception. The legislature today is truly not independent of the Executive and therefore, is often incapacitated from acting as the watchdog of executive activities in a way that will promote a robust accountability system in the executive arm. Thus, the inordinate ambition of members and leadership of the legislative houses often sees them hobnobbing with the executive such that valuable time for law-making is lost in the process of lobbying for juicy leadership positions and committees in the legislative houses (Felix Okwonkwo, Director Microeconomic Dept. FMF, interviewed 10th March, 2024).

In the same vein, Ibrahim Williams in a similar interview (2024) added that the issue of corruption and Nepotism is another challenge before the legislative oversight role that would have evoked high level executive accountability. Nigeria has a poor reputation on corruption and nepotism. This does not exclude the legislature, as members of the National Assembly have been severally accused of bribery and corruption in the exercise of oversight functions. An example is the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) investigation which was carried out by the House of Representatives in the 7th Assembly. Arising from the crash of the stock market and the concomitant loss of the several billions of Naira, the House of Representatives commenced a probe on the activities of the SEC which is the regulatory body of the stock market.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study found that corruption and leadership collusion by both the legislatures and executive during appropriation, approvals and management of infrastructural development funds to be the major challenge weakening legislative oversight and in extension the accountability of the executive. Beside the issue of corruption and collusion, the study equally noticed other debilitating challenges like the issue where the MDAs supply inaccurate information ostensibly to either impress the National Assembly of good performance or to attract the sympathy of the legislative body for increased budgetary allocation; The issue of nepotism and Ethnic loyalty; Personal interests and ambition of the legislators, lack of co-operation and conflicts in the performance of oversight functions between the executive and legislature, lack of solid legislative framework for oversight. Inefficient monitoring and evaluation of infrastructural projects and docile citizenry as the challenges that hinders legislative oversight and in extension equally weaken the executive accountability. This was demonstrated in the survey responses were majority of the respondents about 85.8% argued that the issue of Corruption, nepotism and Ethnic loyalty is a challenge that hinders executive accountability as against only 14.2% who were opposed to this view. More so, about 86.1% of respondents argue that lack of solid legislative framework for oversight is a challenge that hinders executive accountability, whereas only 13.9% respondents held the minority view on this question. The implication was that the path to the legislative oversight role that would adequately monitor, evaluate and investigate the executive toward better accountability was strewed with multiple challenges that hampered and still hinders oversight and accountability on part of the executive.

CONCLUSION

As a matter of fact, most legislatures have developed constitutional mechanisms and tools designed to facilitate the performance of their oversight functions in relation to the executive branch. The performance of this role is done through a wide range of channels, organizations and structures. Notably, the appropriation process provides an important

opportunity for the legislature to exercise legislative oversight. Through the legislative power of the purse, all the Committees, particularly the public account Committees, has a chance to play prominent roles in oversight and can influence executive behaviour and government policy direction in the process.

Experience so far has shown that both public account committees in the National Assembly have not lived up to expectation in the area of oversight. This notwithstanding, it is apt to emphasize that accountability is a collective role of all governmental organs discharging their duties diligently. However, the legislature remains the most prominent actor in facilitating it through oversight, the success of which to a large extent depends on the organization, capacity, and strong will of such legislature. The general challenges that were observed in the study were however seen to be surmountable if the following recommendations are considered and applied.

RECOMMENDATION

The National Assembly must establish its own independent network or machinery through which requisite information and data about the activities of various governmental ministries, Departments and Agencies could be generated. Relying on information and data provided by the MDAs the legislators are supposed to monitor is not only unhealthy but can also be counterproductive. Undoubtedly, the current practice wherein the bulk of the information required by the legislative body to perform its oversight functions is provided by the Presidency through the MDAs has been one of the reasons for the ineffectiveness and inefficiency of the legislative body in the performance of its legislative oversight functions. This is because the MDAs are more disposed to supplying inaccurate information, ostensibly either to impress the National Assembly of good performance or to attract the sympathy of the legislative body for increased budgetary allocation.

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